

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Heterogeneous Catalyst

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Abstract:

Heterogeneous catalysis plays a vital role in present-day chemical industries and supports numerous large-scale operations related to energy production, petrochemical processing, and environmental remediation. Despite its industrial importance, the systematic design of efficient catalysts is still difficult because catalytic reactions are governed by several interconnected factors operating at different length and time scales, including electronic interactions, surface processes, reaction pathways, and mass and heat transport at the reactor level. When combined with first-principles simulations and experimental results, ML (Machine Learning) can lower computational costs and allow researchers to explore a wider range of catalysts. Heterogeneous catalysis, ML has been used for tasks like discovering new catalysts quickly, predicting adsorption energies, modeling reaction rates, evaluating uncertainties, and supporting automated experiments. Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly influencing heterogeneous catalysis by accelerating atomistic simulations, kinetic modeling, and experimental analysis. A persistent challenge is the connection between intrinsic reaction kinetics and experimentally accessible observables, due to the multiscale nature of catalytic systems and the indirect character of measurements. Recent progress in machine-learned force fields, micro kinetic modeling, reactor simulations, and operand techniques enables rapid exploration of large chemical and parameter spaces. Ambiguity persists as multiple mechanisms fit the same data, while AI-driven self-driving models enable rapid catalyst prediction and optimization.

Keywords: Catalyst, Machine Learning (ML), Reaction Pathway, Petrochemical, Adsorption Energy, Kinetic modeling

Introduction:

Catalysis plays a central role in chemical processes, energy conversion, and environmental solutions. Traditional catalyst development mostly uses trial-and-error experiments and complex simulations, which are costly and slow [1]. Recent improvements in machine learning (ML) are reshaping how catalysts can be predicted, screened, and optimized by learning patterns from data instead of only relying on human intuition or exhaustive calculations [1]. AI and machine learning are widely applied in catalysis for materials discovery, reaction network generation, autonomous experimentation, and data mining [2–5]. Despite these advances, most approaches do not fully address the coupling between electronic structure, surface chemistry, kinetics, and reactor-scale transport. Mechanistic

interpretation therefore still relies strongly on expert intuition, limiting reproducibility and scalability [6–8]. Catalysis plays a key role in today's chemical industry and in the development of processes aimed at sustainability [9–12]. Among various reactions, the hydrogenation of nitro aromatic compounds is of major industrial relevance. However, evaluating and comparing the performance of different catalysts reported in the literature is difficult because studies use a wide range of catalyst compositions, reaction conditions, and reporting methods [13–26]. The development of effective catalysts has traditionally depended on trial-and-error methods, which are slow and inefficient due to the intricate phenomena occurring at catalyst surfaces. AI-based techniques offer a data-centric solution to these challenges by enabling rapid assessment and prediction of catalyst

behavior. These data-driven approaches have achieved notable success in many scientific fields, including materials science, chemistry, healthcare, and advanced technologies. Within heterogeneous catalysis, AI allows fast and reliable prediction of important parameters such as adsorption energies, surface characteristics, adsorption isotherms, catalyst composition, and final product Quality. Contrast to conventional mechanistic models that depend on explicit physical equations, AI models extract patterns directly from data[27-28]. Intrinsic kinetic models rely on several hypothesis that are often difficult to do verification, including the nature of active sites, reaction pathways, thermodynamic parameters, and mass or heat transport effect. Because of these impurities, very different sets of atomistic descriptions and kinetic constants can produce the same observable experimental behavior, creating a many-to-one relationship between theoretical models and measured data [29-33]. To properly evaluate model reliability, it is therefore necessary to perform extensive, automated analysis across large ensembles of models in order to quantify sensitivity and uncertainty. In addition, the application of advanced machine-learning models in heterogeneous catalysis is constrained by their limited interpretability. These models often function as complex computational frameworks, making it difficult to clearly explain how specific chemical descriptors influence catalytic activity, selectivity, or stability. This lack of transparency reduces their ability to deliver meaningful chemical insight for rational catalyst design [1]. Many advanced ML techniques function as complex computational frameworks, making it difficult to clearly understand how input features influence catalytic performance. This lack of transparency restricts their ability to provide meaningful chemical insight [1].

The study demonstrates that descriptor-based EDA can extract meaningful insights from heterogeneous literature data. The MIRA21 framework provides a robust, bias-reduced foundation for catalyst ranking and supports future

machine-learning applications in heterogeneous catalysis.[34].

Supervised Learning Applications: Supervised machine learning is used when experimental results are already known. These studies show that machine learning can identify chemical trends and support experiments, even when the dataset size is not very large, especially when chemical understanding is included [35-36].

Unsupervised Learning Applications: Unsupervised learning does not require labeled output data. Instead, it looks for patterns in the data by grouping or reducing dimensions. Although this approach is not widely used in catalysis, it is useful for exploring chemical space and understanding catalyst behavior [37-41]. For instance, clustering methods have been applied to group aryl bromides to select representative reactions. Similar techniques have also been used to identify ligand groups capable of forming certain metal species. In one important study, unsupervised learning helped in discovering new Pd(I) dimer catalysts with very little experimental screening [42].

Applications in Heterogeneous Catalysis:

Adsorption energy plays an important role in deciding how active a catalyst will be. Density Functional Theory (DFT) gives reliable values but it needs a lot of computational time. To overcome this limitation, deep learning methods are used, as they can learn the connection between atomic-level descriptors and adsorption energies more quickly.[43].

In heterogeneous catalysis, nanoporous materials are highly valued because they provide extremely large accessible surface areas. Surface area measurements are usually carried out using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method; however, this method can produce overestimated results, especially for complex structures such as metal–organic frameworks (MOFs)[44]

AI in Catalyst Discovery and Hydrodesulfurization:

Machine learning techniques are increasingly used in catalyst development by analyzing experimental data obtained from atomic-level modifications and reaction performance studies. Using such data, AI models have been able to identify promising ruthenium-based catalysts for ammonia decomposition and improve hydrodesulfurization efficiency by predicting sulfur levels under different operating conditions [45].

In addition, real-time AI-driven control strategies support industrial hydrodesulfurization units by providing continuous online predictions through time-series process data, leading to better process monitoring and optimization. [45-] In recent years, AI has been combined with high-throughput experimentation in different areas of catalysis. This includes heterogeneous systems, homogeneous reactions, and electrochemical catalysis. Using this approach, many catalyst samples can be tested together. [46]

Conclusion:

The use of machine learning together with experimental methods is gradually improving research in heterogeneous catalysis. By connecting experimental results with predictive models, catalyst performance such as activity, selectivity, and stability can be evaluated more efficiently. The combination of data-based modeling, reaction pathway analysis, reactor studies, and modern experimental techniques helps in better understanding surface reactions and reaction kinetics in solid catalysts. However, some practical difficulties still exist. Despite these challenges, ongoing improvements in automated laboratory systems, better organization of experimental data, and more understandable machine-learning methods are expected to increase the usefulness of AI in heterogeneous catalysis. These developments will help in making heterogeneous catalysts that are more stable, and eco-friendly, while also improving the

connection between experimental work and data-based studies in catalysis research.

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